

Paper 3

A STUDY ON REINVENTION AND CHALLENGES OF IBM

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Abstract

International Business Machine Corporation (IBM) is one of the first multinational conglomerates to emerge in the US-headquartered in Armonk, New York. IBM was established in 1911 in Endicott, New York, as Computing-Tabulating-Recording Company (CTR). In 1924, CTR was renamed IBM. Big Blue has been IBM's nickname since 1980. IBM started with the production of scales, punch cards, data processors and time clock now produce and sells computer hardware and software, middleware, provides hosting and consulting services. It has a worldwide presence, operating in over 175 nations with 3,50,600 staff with \$79.6 billion in annual income (Dec 2018). It is currently competing with Microsoft, Google, Apple, and Amazon. 2012 to 2017 was tough time for IBM, although it invests in the field of research where it faced challenges while trying to stay relevant in rapidly changing Tech-Market. While 2018 has been relatively better and attempting to regain its place in the IT industry. With 3,000 scientists, it invests 7% of its total revenue to Research & Development in 12 laboratories across 6 continents. This resulted in the U.S. patent leadership in IBM's 26th consecutive year. In 2018, out of the 9,100 patents that granted to IBM 1600 were related to Artificial Intelligence and 1,400 related to cyber-security. In artificial intelligence, blockchain, safety/security, cloud technology, nano-technology, quantum computing, silicon, and post-silicon computing architecture IBM researchers are doing pioneering job. In this paper, we will discuss Global Market, Strategies, Services, Contribution to Research, Social Responsibility, and Finance.

Keywords: IBM, Computing-Tabulating-Recording, Big Blue, Reinvention, Challenges.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over a whole century, IBM has developed into a worldwide incorporated company from a small business which manufactures scales, time clocks & tabulations. IBM is a multinational conglomerate company based in the United States founded by Ranlett Flint and Thomas J. Watson currently Virginia M. Rometty as the current Chairman, President and CEO [1]. Established in Endicott, New York in June 1911, by the consolidation of three companies, the Tabulating Machine Company, the International Time Recording Company and the Computing Scale Company, as a

new company known as the Computing-Tabulating-Recording Company (CTR). CTR was renamed International Business Machine Corporation in 1924.

Headquarters moved to Armonk, New York, in the next few years. It was subsequently renamed IBM. It plays a major role in medical science, data technology, electronics, communication and mechanical systems innovation and growth. It is not limited to one specific sector and is engaged with the implementation of high-end technology in every prominent sector. Although it grew steadily, in the past eight to ten years it confronted its problems. IBM's 2018 income and operating income of \$79.6 billion per share amounted to \$13.81 [2]. For the entire year we returned to sales development, income per share increased and margins were stabilized even though it has competitions from Microsoft, Google, Apple, Amazon and many more. Nicknamed as "Big Blue," IBM is one of 30 Dow Jones industry average firms with over 350,600 staff and is one of the world's largest companies, known as "IBMer." There are at least 70% of IBMers outside the U.S. and India has the highest IBMers. IBM's staff won five Nobel Prizes, six Turing Awards, ten National Technology Medals(USA) and five National Science Medals (USA) for their contribution [3].

2. PRODUCTS AND MILESTONES

In order to develop in different fields, IBM manufactured numerous products and innovation. Trust in science, pursuit of understanding and belief in making world function better together.

- **1928: U.S. Census and Punch Card.** It has been used as storage instruments and it has enabled a U.S. census.
- **1932: The IBM Service Bureau** is set up to support businesses that do not permit IBM machines to be purchased. It helped many small companies
- **1936: IBM enables social security.** IBM cooperates with the state to draw up records of 26 million Americans on the US Social Security Act of 1935.
- **1937: International Test Scoring Machine IBM Type 805** gave way to familiar test sheets of fill-in the bubble.
- **1952: Digital storage start-up.** IBM enables magnetic tape to become a feasible data storage device that introduces the concept of digital storage to the globe.
- **1953: The world's first effective open-heart surgery on a person was done by the first heart and lung machinery.**
- **1956: First IBM 704 self-study program.** The notion of artificial intelligence is regarded as the first demonstration.
- **1957: FORTRAN** opens the door to modern information technology..
- **1961: The launching of speech recognition device *Shoebox*.**
- **1962: SABRE: ecommerce's genesis.** The first computer-driven airline booking scheme is launched by IBM and American Airlines..
- **1969: IBM constructs PC's and writes many of the complicated Apollo mission software programmes.**
- **1970: The Magnetic swipe strip.** The start of IBM's magnetic credit card swipe strip changes the way business is done.

- **1971: The world's first floppy disc.** First portable, affordable, powerful Storage device is created.
- **1973: The Universal Product Code.** UPC is 12 digit number given to particular product. Because of it business sector rapidly changed since we can track every orders.
- **1980: IBM patents LASIK surgery.** They can write on human hair with lasers very accurate. LASIK surgery is improving sight and quality of life for millions of individuals not only in the matter of quality but it is also cost efficient and time efficient in nature.
- **1981: IBM PC** introduction. The PC revolution starts with IBM Personal Computer's debut, the most economical and smallest computer ever.
- **1986:** The Nobel prize is awarded to **scanning tunnel microscopes** that are ultimately used in manipulating nuclear energy
- **1997: IBM Deep Blue** a supercomputer which used the Artificial Intelligence and defeated the champion in the field of chess
- **2011: first liquid language comprehension AI.** Jeopardy, the champion of TV-quiz! **IBM Watson** is derided. In his unprecedented demonstration of natural voice recognition and cognitive computation, Watson rightly acknowledges and responds to colloquialism, jokes and sarcasm. Transactions are implemented.
- **2018: The Summit of supercomputing.** Summit is a supercomputer which is present at Oak Ridge National laboratories created with Integration of Artificial Intelligence for the purpose to support all the technologies reaches speeds of 200 petaflops [4].

3. FINANCIALS

We will be using financial statements and annual report to analyze company's status. In the table contains the financial statement (Revenue and Net Income) and Number of Employees from 2014-2018 [2][5][6]. IBMs annual revenue is took a huge dip from 2014-2016 because of it brand value was also decreased. IBM has seen decreased profits and revenue is therefore attempting to restructure its company model, which could partially explain how present staff is decreasing. In 2018, the American technology firm IBM employed about 350, 600 individuals around the globe, and over the previous six years there has been a general downward trend of staff[2]. IBM has faced a class action suit since early 2019 claiming that it breaches federal legislation against age discrimination while IBM maintains that it takes skills-based choices in its jobs. In the economic areas, fiscal 2018, Q1 and Q2 2019 are a bit better, with the trend slowly stabilizing and rebounding. IBM is acquiring / merging with different companies of different size in different field so that it can use their market and can have strong foot in different field. In 2018, IBM has acquired Red Hat with U.S. \$34 million which has prominent in field of cloud and open source. A numbers of drastic steps were required to decrease the loss business, such as decreasing the amount of staff, financing research areas etc. From the table given we can see the decrease in Revenue, Net Income, and Number of Employees etc. Revenues of U.S. \$18.2 billion and U.S. \$19.2 billion respectively were generated in the first and second quarters of 2019 [7] [8]. With a total of U.S. \$37.4 billion in two quarters, with enormous contribution from field of cloud and cognitive software.

Table 1: Revenue, Net Income, Employees With respect to Year [2] [5] [6]

Year	Revenue (in mil. \$ U.S.)	Net Income (in mil. \$ U.S.)	No. of Employees
2014	92793	12022	379592
2015	81741	13190	377757
2016	79919	38294	380300
2017	79139	36943	366600
2018	79591	36936	350600

4. IBM CLOUD GARAGE

Cloud computing is about the use of remote server networks in data storage, administration and processing. Recently most of the software / applications are shifting from data centers to cloud because of its ease of use and low maintaining cost. Cloud computing produces billions of dollars annually in income as a section of IT services and shows little sign of a slowdown. In 2017, public cloud market share was U.S. \$146 Billion in 2019 market grown by 17.5% with cloud data center ip traffic growth of 10.6ZB/yr. in 2018 [9].

IBM cloud has very little Public Cloud market share but it is better in private and hybrid clouds and it is expected to grow since people are shifting from public cloud to private and hybrid cloud. Although it is very late in entering the cloud market and faces strong competitions from giants like Amazon, Alibaba, Microsoft and Google it is striving hard to do better. IBM generated about \$1.14 billion in income from its hosting of true private cloud services in 2017, making it a market share of around 12% more than other true private cloud providers [10]. In 2018 and 2019, cloud and cognitive software is a major contributor to the stabilization of IBM. In the 1st and 2nd Quarter, cloud and cognitive software contributed \$5.0 billion and \$5.6 billion [7][8]. In 2018, Red Hat Company was bought for U.S. \$34 million, a company which is well known for open source and cloud services, and is therefore expected to do better [11]. IBM uses a cloud garage technique to enhance customer services where workshops are conducted so that client can take advantage of it.

As mentioned in the fig1 IBM cloud garage is mainly made up of Themes, workflows, and practices which cover the entire lifecycle of software delivery from start to finish, including the collection and response of client feedback and changing markets [12]. Different customer may require cloud with different functionality and architecture which they can fully utilize. In IBM garage clients will be helped by the business model which is

currently in use and experts so that they can create and implement their own architecture. This will be specific and unique to them.

Themes: Following prescriptive pathways for Cloud transformation goals: Advise, Build, Move, and Manage.

Workflows: Practice procedures from beginning to end in order to achieve goal.

Practices: Culture, Discover, Envision, Develop, Reason, Operate, and Learn.

Fig 1: IBM Cloud Garage [12]

5. SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESEARCH

5.1. Research

IBM is one of the companies which contribute hugely on Research so that it can innovate new ideas, products and be responsible for the development of society. It utilizes 7% of Total Revenue for Research and Development. But since they are going through rough patch for the financial contribution was decreased in fiscal year 2018. The Group has employed 3,000 scientists/researchers in 12 laboratories on six continents, working in the areas of Artificial Intelligence, Quantum Computing, Block-Chain, Safety/Security, Cloud Computing, Nanotechnology, Silicon & post-Silicon Computing Architecture mainly concentrates in the field of Financial Services, Health Care, Internet of Things and Block-Chain. As a result of its contribution to Research and Development produced more than 100000 patents since 1993. For the consecutive 26 years it is leading in number of patents. In 2018, IBM was awarded with 9,100 patents out of which 3,000 belong to the field of AI, Cloud, Cyber Security, Quantum Computing. Different techniques / fields are made to combine so that clients can achieve maximum results and boundary between fields can be broken [2] [5] [6].

5.2. Social Responsibilities

IBM is one of the biggest companies of the century and generates \$79 billion in total revenue in 2018. It never forgets its social responsibility, recognizes its worldwide significance fully and continually contributes to society. Some of them are listed below

IBM is Founding member of “Call for Code” in 2018. Where more than 100,000 developers from 156 countries globally competed. They have built over 2500 applications with IBM Cloud technology to reduce impact of natural disaster.

In order to avoid illegal human trading a by using analytical software, IBM has entered a pact with "STOP THE TRAFFIK" Law Enforcement and Financial Services Institution, which recognizes suspected patterns, hotspots, and financial transactions. It has also introduced

"**AI Fairness 360**", an open source toolkit to help designers actively detect and reduce deformation and misrepresentations of information sets because of Artificial Intelligence.

It also has 12 months training program in the field of education, including cyber security, digital design, mainframe administration and software development, through the implementation of the "**IBM Apprenticeship Program**". The program has included training and online work experience, guided by an IBM mentor, led by hundreds of apprentices. Stated **Skills Build an IBM voluntary** initiative that allows more than 3 million students to know about new and advanced technology in primary and secondary schools. Early College High School in 200 colleges with over 125,000 in 13 nations in the 11 U.S. States, "**Pathways to technology (P-TECH)**". It also conducts workshops regularly. It is also took the initiative to train people with disability so they can work in IT company without any difficulty [2].

IBM is working with many Government Institutions where it is helping them in the field of data security and improves the skills of officials by periodic training. In 2018 IBMers spent 1.3 M hrs as volunteer and donated \$24 Million [13].

6. REINVENTIONS

IBM is facing the rough patch in last 8 years, and it is just trying to stabilize itself. As a result it is also trying to take some of the drastic steps. Number of Employees currently working at IBM has been continuously decreasing from year 2017 so that they will not have huge burden. Since it was using enormous amount of money on research since past decade the new research work are starting to take shape. Company is also hoping because of the new products which will be concentrating on Artificial Intelligence, Quantum Computing, Blockchain, Security, Cloud Technology will be able to take back the market.

6.1. Integrated Solutions

IBM has been engaged in various technologies such as cloud, AI, security etc. IBM therefore provides its customers embedded alternatives and products to use other technologies. Since it is working in different fields transition or integrating solutions is pretty easy. The end product will also have benefits since it contains characteristics of many techniques.

6.2. Strategic Business Units

IBM is spreading out on wide categories of projects that have helped the business focus and to compete with its strong competitors as well as keeping ahead of them. They are present in different fields they can identify the business opportunity very quickly and since they are working in different fields combining of solutions will be also very easy.

6.3. Migration to Higher Technology

IBM is doing the researches on new technology like AI, Cloud, Security, Blockchain for a very long time so shifting to higher technology will not be a problem to them. Shifting to new technologies has attracted many customers.

6.4. Data Analytics

Increasing IBM capacity in data analytics has invested over U.S. \$30 billion i.e. One third of their research expenditure relates to data analysis and cognitive computing [14].

7. CHALLENGES

7.1. Differentiating its Hardware from Rivals

IBM has many competitors like Dell, Intel etc. who are making the similar products. So it is unable to make its customer differentiate between them. When the hardware is not brought by the customers Software's which is coming together it will also not be brought.

7.2. Dip in Global Technology / Business Services

Hosting and consulting services are provided by IBM. There is enormous competition from many companies offering the same sort of services. Global technology and business services revenues decreased by 10% in 2018. Cloud rivalry is also enormous, even if the private and hybrid IBM cloud has been doing better; it was late for market access.

7.3. Data Privacy

Since it is working on cloud and data analytics it will be dealing with huge amount of data. And obviously customers will be having doubts about the security of the Data.

8. SWOT ANALYSIS

To be able to understand how the business operates in the market so that we can concentrate on companies strengths, the weakness of our business in this area or we can work on them and weakness can be changed into opportunity or strength, the opportunity for us to understand which products or type we need so that we can focus on particular area of industry at the same time and utilize it. The threat of knowing factors which will cause harm to the company so that they can be avoided. SWOT analysis is used to comprehend inner and external product or company influencing factors and how can they used in our advantage.

8.1. Strengths

- **Brand Strengths:** In 2018, IBM was at 12th Place. The brand was decreased by 8% and value was U.S \$42.97 Billion with top performing factors commitment, Responsiveness and consistency [15].
- **Business Model:** IBM focuses on long term growth strategy. It focuses on innovation, efficiency, competitiveness so that it will be able to provide long term advantages.
- **Being Updated:** IBM is keeping on changing regularly with technology so that it can keep up with demands of the world. It acquires company which is doing well and uses new technology like AI, Cloud, Blockchain etc. Recently it has acquired Red Hat for U.S. \$34Million.

- **Data Analytics:** IBM deals with data analysis and cognitive computing, it realizes the importance of it and allocates more or less one-third of its Research and Development budget.
- **Middleware Market:** IBM is leading the middleware market with 30% market share. The application infrastructure middleware market was valued at USD 29.38 billion in 2018 and is expected to reach a value of USD 44.54 billion by 2024 [16],
- **Research and Development:** IBM has committed R&D facility with 12 labs across 6 continents. It is providing 7% of its total revenue to Research where it working in new technologies like AI, Cloud, Blockchain, Security etc [2].

8.2. Weakness

- **Brand Value Drop:** In the last 5-8 years IBM is going through rough patch where its total revenue decreased as a result brand value also took its hit.
- **Litigations:** IBM has been continuously involved in litigations and disputes which in turn decreases brand value. This will be also responsible in decreasing faith in company.
- **Analysis:** Since IBM is a multinational company which works in most of the fields analyzing, finding problem and solution becomes difficult.

8.3. Opportunities:

- **Data Analytics:** The assessment of Data analytics market is \$125 billion. IBM is investing U.S. \$1 billion in Watson, \$100 million for start-ups building cognitive applications. It also integrates with Twitter into the cloud-based analytics of IBM.
- **Cloud-Based Solutions:** Cloud computing services demand is increasing and is set to reach over \$1.9 billion by 2018. Public cloud services are expected to expand at 33%. IBM is doing well in Private and Hybrid Cloud.
- **Business Expansion:** The Company has purchased 23 mobile, social and security-based companies. IBM and Apple have partnered for easy-to-use private applications in the business setting. The company's activities can be expanded.
- **Consulting Business:** Even though IBM consulting business has been decreased by 10%. IBM is expecting to invest in consulting business by seeing its opportunity.

8.4. Threats

- **Competition:** Since IBM is involved in different fields it has more competitors. In cloud it has the competitors like Amazon, Google, Microsoft, Alibaba etc. In Technology with HP, Dell, Intel, EMC, Cisco Systems etc. In software business with Oracle, SAP, CA etc. some other companies are Accenture, Xerox, CSC, Fujitsu, Infosys and Wipro etc.
- **Global Economy:** In the face of global turbulence, the multinational company must ensure that prices of raw materials, labor, shipments etc. remain inspected to ensure competitive pricing. This also changes the currency that can influence its income and income per share [17].

9. CONCLUSION

In the past eight years, IBM remains one of the best multinationals with an extremely strong reputation and social engagement. Its annual revenue may have fallen but still retains profit by taking some dramatic steps with a slight deviation. In 2019, IBM decided to evaluate its trimester development so that it could make clear progress and take action against adverse events. As the

trend moves from the public cloud to the private cloud where IBM is doing better, it will develop more rapidly. IBM's cloud garage technique helps the client with the assistance of mentors / company specialists to create better product. IBM also helps researchers move to greater technology, which attracts more clients. It is feasible to produce better and more effective products by integrating between distinct techniques.

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